

EFFECT OF PLY-SCALE DEFECTS ON THE COMPRESSIVE FAILURE OF CARBON-FIBRE REINFORCED POLYMERS

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ABSTRACT

This work investigated the influence of manufacturing method on the observed compressive strength of a unidirectional CFRP laminate. Laminates produced using RIFT were found to demonstrate the lowest compressive strength due their comparably low fibre volume fraction and abundance of resin-rich regions. The application of an overpressure during the cure cycle was shown to be an effective way to increase the global fibre volume fraction within the resulting laminate; this enables laminates cured with an increased overpressure to realise the highest strengths observed in this work. Secondly, this work investigated the systematic implementation of ply-scale defects on the longitudinal compressive strength of otherwise unidirectional (UD) CFRP laminates. Compression testing of CFRPs manufactured showed monotonic reduction of compressive strength and strain with increasing number of defected plies, before plateauing at a low threshold. The failure mode and location of defected-CFRPs was significantly more consistent than UD-CFRPs, with lower variation in compressive failure parameters measured. The results suggest a role for the concept of strategic defects, both in terms of improving the valid failure rate of the standard test, reducing test time, and in terms of incorporating pre-designed failure sites in critical components, minimising the amount of inspection and validation required across component lifetimes.

1 INTRODUCTION

All too often, industry tends to take strength values reported on data sheets at face value, without accounting for the manufacturing process used. For now, simply at an anecdotal level, it is known that nominally identical laminates produced via different manufacturing routes can display vastly different mechanical properties. This paper aims to explain how and why that is via analysis of composite laminates at the microscale.

While the tensile behaviour of unidirectional laminates is reasonably well understood, compressive failure remains a controversial subject. The lack of knowledge and confidence surrounding compressive failure is one the primary factors why most composite design remains bound by the expensive and time consuming 'make and test' philosophy. When manufacturing a composite laminate, the existence of manufacturing defects is regarded as inevitable.

1.1 Theories of compressive failure

Kink-band formation due to fibre microbuckling is the most common failure mode of fibre reinforced polymers (FRPs) under longitudinal compression. Rosen [1] identified fibre microbuckling as the primary cause of failure in FRPs and was the first to model this mechanism in a systematic way; by considering the composite as an array of equi-spaced, parallel bars with an elastic matrix in between. When subject to axial compressive loading, the fibres displace in both an extension and a shear mode. For fibre volume fractions greater than 30%, as is the case with modern high-strength composites, the shear mode dominates, and the fibres deform transversely in phase. The associated failure stress is therefore given by Equation 1.

$$X_C = \frac{G_m}{1-v_f} \quad (1)$$

This model, and further refinements based on elastic buckling theory, tend to considerably overpredict the compressive strength of fibre reinforced polymers; typically, by a factor of two to four for state-of-the-art carbon and glass fibre reinforced composites. One of the first models to incorporate implicitly plastic microbuckling of initially curved fibres is described by Argon [2]. This initial degree of fibre misalignment, θ_i , leads to shear stresses within the surrounding matrix which would, in turn, increase the degree of misalignment, ultimately resulting in the local buckling of fibres; a failure mode analogous to kink bands in metal crystals. It was with Argon's model, Equation 2, via the acknowledgement of initial local instabilities within the fibres, that the quantitative agreement of predictions began improving significantly.

$$X_C = \frac{G_m}{\theta_i} \quad (2)$$

Following Argon, many models were proposed for fibre kinking due to similar principles, considering an initial degree of fibre misalignment and shear yielding of the matrix. Among others, Wang [3], Budiansky et al. [4], and Hahn and Williams [5], all progressed the shear instability model of Argon. Each of these models is based on analysis of an initially geometrically imperfect fibre in bending, under the action of a non-symmetric compressive load and shearing stresses transmitted via the surrounding matrix material. It is now worth noting that models suggesting shear instability mostly yielded reasonable agreement with experimental data on a semi-empirical basis only. A strength prediction a priori was not possible due to a lack of information regarding the initial fibre waviness; the initial fibre deflection was a free parameter which allowed for fitting of test results. It was not until Yugartis in 1987 [6] that a technique to quantify fibre angle distributions was proposed.

A recent attempt at modelling kink band formation, conducted by Pimenta et al. [7], is based on the equilibrium of an initially misoriented fibre, laterally supported by an elasto-plastic matrix and is given by Equation 3. The governing equations on which this model is based are derived from the equilibrium of a single fibre within the composite, with an initially small, localised imperfection. Away from the imperfection, fibres are assumed to be straight throughout the analysis. It is assumed the fibre behaves according to classical beam theory, with the surrounding matrix resisting only shear stresses. The behaviour of the composite is modelled from the start of compression to the onset of fibre failure. The composite compressive strength is defined as the peak load per unit thickness and is given by Equation 3.

$$X_C = S_M \frac{G_m^{2D} \cdot \phi_f + \frac{\pi^2}{L^2} E_f I_f}{S_M + \pi \cdot \frac{y_0}{L} \cdot G_m^{2D}} \cdot \frac{v_f^{2D}}{A_f} \quad (3)$$

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Laminate manufacturing process

The initial manufacturing route studied in this work was Resin Infusion under Flexible Tooling (RIFT). RIFT is a cheap, widely accessible composite fabrication method. To manufacture the composite laminates using RIFT, 10 plies of unidirectional fabric were laid up on a flat heated mould. The dry stack of fabrics was then covered with release film, a resin flow medium and placed in a vacuum bag. Resin was then infused via vacuum over a period of 20 minutes and subsequently cured under vacuum for 16 hours at 80°C.

Fibres pre-impregnated with epoxy resin (prepreg) were subsequently used to produce laminates out-of-autoclave (OOA) (subject to only vacuum pressure). Prepreg fibres are much cleaner to work with than dry fibres and liquid resin and have considerably better health and safety characteristics. There are also further opportunities for lay-up automation associated with the use of prepreg fibres. Despite this, prepreg fibres are also associated with a much higher material cost than liquid resin infusion techniques. Thus, there is an economic push to move towards low-cost fabrication techniques rather than continuing

to rely on high-cost prepreg technology. In this work, the prepreg used was composed of Toray T700 high strength fibres pre-impregnated with epoxy resin. The fabric was laid up on a heated mould, debulked under vacuum pressure for 2 hours and cured for 4 hours at 100°C.

The effect of autoclaving was also investigated. Laminates were produced using prepreg fibres in-autoclave (subject to an overpressure of 3 or 6 bar). This work utilised a press-clave to replicate in-autoclave curing conditions. Prepreg fibre tapes were laid up on the mould surface and debulked under vacuum pressure for 2 hours. A retaining force was then applied to the lid of the press-clave using a Shimadzu testing machine, and the internal cavity was pressurised to either 3 or 6 bar using compressed air. The mould surface was then heated to 80°C and the laminate cured for 16 hours.

2.2 Compression test fixture

The test fixture employed in this work was the ICSTM test fixture developed by Haberle [8]. The ICSTM test fixture employs a tabbed specimen loaded principally on the ends, similar to the modified ASTM D695 specimen [9], to remove the issues associated with waisting and transverse specimen failure common in previous fixtures [8]. In this configuration, a percentage of the load is transmitted by shear via the end tabs, having the effect of lowering the average stresses at the end of the test piece. The fixture itself is based on the one developed at Birmingham University with several changes. As seen in **Figure 1**, the fixture is composed of two blocks to hold the specimen ends. These blocks serve to prevent end tab debonding, sample 'brooming' due to shear failure of the end, and compression failure under the end tab. The base of the fixture is made from hardened steel to prevent indentations on the loading surfaces due to the high compressive stresses that can be realised by CFRP. A further advantage of this die set is its relative simplicity and off-the-shelf availability.

Figure 1: Annotated ISCTM test fixture used at FAC Technology, (a) alongside an exploded view, (b), taken directly from [8] for comparison.

2.2 Measurement of small angle misalignment

Though aligned largely in the same direction within a ply, continuous fibre composites display small angular misalignment about their mean direction. The presence of this misalignment has been recognised for many years and its influence on the mechanical properties of composite materials acknowledged extensively. An effective method for the quantification of fibre misalignment is therefore essential if proper composite strength modelling is to be carried out. The technique proposed by Yugartis [6], whose

method is based on the observation that the plane section of a circular cylinder is an ellipse, was used to evaluate the degree of fibre misorientation present in the laminates studied.

3 RESULTS

3.1 RIFT versus out-of-autoclave versus in-autoclave

Laminates produced using RIFT realised significantly lower strengths than those produced using prepreg fibres as shown in Figure 2 (a). There is a significant difference in fibre volume fraction between the RIFT manufactured laminates and the OOA and pressclave manufactured laminates. This prompted an investigation into the microstructure of laminates produced using each method, firstly focusing on the effects of fibre misorientation and its distribution, and subsequently the influence of fibre volume fraction, on the measured compressive strength.

The influence of fibre orientation on the observed composite compressive strength was initially evaluated by normalising the average strength by the global fibre volume fraction (evaluated as $X_c^{V_f} = \frac{F^*}{V_f A}$). This normalization, presented in Figure 2(b) allows for a comparison of the specimen failure load per fibre area, as opposed to laminate area, hence is a much truer indication of the influence of fibre misorientation on the compressive strength of the laminate. The laminates produced using prepreg fibres all display reasonable agreement, with a maximum difference between observed mean values of only 16%, and a region of overlap between all standard deviations. The mean strength observed in the RIFT laminate, however, is still considerably lower, indicative of a greater degree of initial misorientation.

Figure 2: A comparison of the (a) compressive strength, X_c , and (b) V_f normalised strength, $X_c^{V_f}$, realised by UD laminates produced using each of the fabrication processes under investigation.

3.2 Influence of fibre misorientation

The in-plane and out-of-plane fibre misorientations were subsequently evaluated for each fabrication process studied. Plots of the cumulative angular distribution of the fibres are seen in Figure 3 and are found to be in good agreement with similar work in [6], [8] and [10]. Note the absolute degree of misorientation is plotted as the technique employed does not correlate fibre angle and location, hence positive and negative values are of equal status. The evaluated in-plane misalignment, within laminates produced using prepreg, is consistent, with all evaluated standard deviations within 3% of one another; validating the accuracy of the misalignment technique employed. There is no observed correlation between an increased overpressure and reduced in-plane misalignment. It is therefore concluded that curing with an increased overpressure is not an effective way to reduce the degree of in-plane misorientation.

The largest of the in-plane misalignments was found within the laminates produced using RIFT; this can be attributed to numerous stages of the infusion procedure. Firstly, during the vac-down process, as the vacuum bag shrinks over the dry fibres, whilst the prepreg stack is held in position by the tackiness of the resin, the dry fibres are free to move. This effect can be lessened by securing the fibres to the mould surface with, for example, masking tape, however it should be pointed out even when secured in this manner, some movement of plies was still observed. Additionally, flow of the resin through the fibre stack will also serve to displace the fibres from their original orientation, further increasing the degree of misalignment. Unfortunately, this is an unavoidable feature of liquid resin processing. Considering Figure 3 (b), the laminate produced using RIFT also demonstrates the highest degree of out-of-plane misalignment. While prepreg fibres are held together solely by the tackiness of the resin between them, dry fibres are held together by stitching normal to the fibre direction, hence are inherently sinuous. This is hypothesised to account for much of the variation in ϕ between laminates produced using RIFT and prepreg fibres. Interestingly, and somewhat intuitively, a correlation between an increased overpressure and a reduced degree of out-of-plane misorientation was found; population of this data set with a wider range of overpressures should confirm this conclusion. Despite this, proportional to an increase in overpressure, is an increase in manufacturing cost and complexity. With a larger data set, an optimisation for ϕ reduction as a function of the applied overpressure could be conducted and would be of great industrial significance. This is, therefore, a recommended topic of further investigation.

Figure 3: Cumulative fibre angle distributions for each fabrication process studied.

3.3 Influence of fibre volume fraction

The global fibre volume fraction was obtained by imaging a cross section of a test specimen, measuring the total fibre area in much the same way as the ellipses were identified, and evaluating this as a fraction of the total laminate area, $V_f = A_f/A_{lam}$. In the present investigation, the larger of the misalignments evaluated in the previous section, θ , was used within the Pimenta failure model, as it provides a more conservative estimate of the composite compressive strength.

The failure model developed by Pimenta et al. [7], when implemented using the global fibre volume fraction, and standard deviation of the fibre misalignment, overpredicts the compressive strength of the laminates studied, by a factor of between 1.1 and 1.25, see Figure 4 (a). One way to interpret this finding is that the compressive strength realised by the tested laminates is equivalent to that predicted of laminates with significantly lesser fibre volume fraction. In order to investigate this further, each laminate was divided into five regions of equal size and the volume fraction evaluated within each one. X_c was subsequently plotted against the smallest of the five local fibre volume fractions obtained, for

comparison to the Pimenta et al. failure model, Figure 4 (b). Note, given the uncertainty regarding the exact shear modulus of the resin used within the RIFT process, the blue shaded region indicates the range which could be occupied.

Figure 4: X_c vs V_f both globally and locally for comparison to the Pimenta model, plotted with θ_0 and G_m specific to each laminate

Inspection of Figure 4 (b) reveals far better agreement between the experimental results and the failure model, when compared to Figure 4 (a); with the model predictions lying within one standard deviation of the experimentally obtained mean in all cases.

Heat maps of V_f in these regions were subsequently produced to better quantify the implications on the laminate compressive strength, with the evaluation window chosen as a function of the fibre diameter, d . Note here, there is an optimal window size which is small enough to capture the effects of local changes in V_f , but large enough to encompass enough material such that it is representative of the laminate. In the case of too small an evaluation window, ultra-local volume fractions are analysed such that individual fibres are captured with a V_f of 1, and regions of matrix captured with a V_f of 0; however, as the evaluation window size increases, the local V_f tends to the global V_f . An evaluation window of $10d$ was deemed most appropriate. The heat maps in Figure 5 serve to indicate the inconsistencies within the microstructure of laminates produced using RIFT, when compared to laminates produced using prepreg fibres. The dark blue regions visible in the heat maps of V_f produced in the case of the RIFT laminates are inter-laminar resin layers between plies. In addition to promoting buckling within nearby fibres, these regions act to reduce the inter-laminar shear strength of the composite and encourage delaminations. These regions of low V_f are extremely detrimental to the composite compressive strength, an issue that is less prevalent in the laminates produced using prepreg. As fibres are the primary load carrying component of the composite, resin rich regions are extremely vulnerable to failure. Unfortunately, despite understanding this effect at an anecdotal level, the influence of resin rich regions on the mechanical properties of CFRP composites has not been widely studied [1], hence much of the following analysis is qualitative in nature.

The implications of these findings are as follows. Resin rich regions, particularly within laminates produced using liquid resin processing techniques, are extremely detrimental to the composite compressive strength. Not only do they have the undesirable effect of lowering the global volume fraction, but they also act to encourage local fibre failure. As composite compressive failure is dominated by kink-band initiation (postulated to occur due to a sudden failure event, such as fibre collapse, fibre fracture, or matrix shear yielding) existing failure models are best applied locally, within regions of relative weakness. We have here developed an empirically guided approach that works well, but clearly additional effort is required to base these observations on a proper mechanics informed approach.

Figure 5: Locally mapped V_f and the corresponding X_c , forecast by the Pimenta et al. failure model, for each fabrication process studied. Note the scales are not consistent across each plot to better emphasise variations in V_f and projected V_f .

3.4 Exaggerated local misalignment

In order to investigate the effect of a large degree of local misalignment in an otherwise nominally UD laminate, a 300 gsm ply was 'stepped' over multiple, thinner, 30 gsm plies, with the intention of generating a microstructural defect likely to initiate kink-band formation. The 30 gsm plies were cut to half the laminate length, and the fibre stack was laid up as shown in Figure 6. The specimens produced using this method were marked on the surface at the point of the defect as visible in Figure 7 (a). This served to indicate where the specimen fractured with regards to the defect and, by extension, if failure nucleated at the defect site.

Figure 6: Annotated exploded view of the layup used to produce laminates with a large local defect.

Figure 7: Fractured compression specimen, (a) pre- and (b) post-failure with the silver line indicating the position of the manufactured defect.

By inspection of Figure 8, it is apparent that there is no correlation between the initial defect amplitude and the specimen compressive strength. The strength of the non-defective control laminate lies within one standard deviation of the strengths realised by every laminate studied. Intuitively, as kink band formation is the primary cause of compressive failure, it is reasonable that larger initial degrees of misorientation would be more likely to initiate specimen failure. Though one would assume this would also lead to a reduction in strength, this study did not find that to be the case. It is hypothesised that this can be attributed to a higher fibre volume fraction within the defective laminates, compared to the nominally unidirectional control. The measured specimen thickness was not observed to increase at the rate anticipated with the addition of more thin plies within the laminate, thus implying better laminate consolidation and, in turn, a higher V_f . This was not investigated any further in the present study, however a potential route for further work would be to section these laminates and evaluate V_f .

Figure 8: Compressive strength, X_c , realised by unidirectional laminates manufactured with the central 300 gsm ply stepped over n 30 gsm plies.

The introduction of the out of plane step within the ply had an additional benefit. As seen in Figure 7 (b), failure of the compressed laminate occurred exactly at the point of the introduced out-of-plane defect. The frequency at which failure initiation at the defect site occurred and the frequency of observed valid failures, as per ASTM D6641 [12], were recorded and the results are plotted in Figure 9.

Figure 9: Percentage of (a) valid failures as per ASTM D6441 and (b) failures initiated at the defect site for step magnitudes between 1 and 5 30 gsm plies.

There is a clear correlation between defect amplitude and the frequency by which failure is initiated at the defect site. In addition, photograph of the specimen taken during the experiment further indicated that failure of these laminates was almost always found to be within the central ply, i.e., the failure initiated at the manufactured defect, Figure 10. It is also interesting to note that the observed stiffness of the laminates with the manufactured was statistically the same as those for the laminates where no defect was deliberately introduced. While this is probably intuitive from a simple rule of mixtures calculation, the implication is, until failure, the stress/strain response of the laminate is unaffected by the presence of the defect.

Figure 10: Failure within the central ply of a laminate manufactured with a central laminate defect.

It is interesting that one could introduce an irregularity within the microstructure such that failure at a specified location could be almost guaranteed, without a significant reduction in measured strength. The frequency by which valid failures were observed, as per ASTM D6641 [11], increased dramatically. In the case of the unidirectional control, only 60% of tested specimen yielded valid failures within the gauge section. Compared to the 89% valid failures observed when laminates were manufactured with a defect of amplitude 5 30gsm plies, there is a significantly larger cost and time associated with collecting a given number of datapoints. In a bid to reduce this, a built-in stress concentration could be such that it is large enough to promote failure within the gauge section, yet small enough such that the strength of the defective laminate was still somewhat representative of a nominally perfect laminate. Alternatively, from a commercial standpoint, the ability to know the failure location of the laminate a priori would prove extremely useful. If the likelihood of failure occurring at the defect location can be predicted with 90% certainty, non-critical in-service composite parts need not always be inspected completely, merely at the locations of the fabricated defects. Inspection of the defect site alone would likely reveal failure, at a lesser cost to the business than a complete inspection.

9 CONCLUSIONS

The contrast in measured strengths between laminates produced using RIFT and prepreg fibres can be mostly attributed to the comparatively higher V_f observed in laminates produced using prepreg. Whilst laminates produced using RIFT did display a higher degree of fibre misorientation than laminates produced using prepreg, inconsistencies within the microstructure not observed in laminates produced using prepreg, and a significantly lower V_f , were found to be more detrimental to the measured compressive strength. The application of an overpressure during the cure cycle was shown to be an effective way to reduce the out-of-plane fibre misorientation and increase the global V_f within the resulting laminate. These enabled laminates cured with an increased overpressure to realise the highest strengths observed in this work.

The failure model developed by Pimenta et al. was shown to be in good agreement with strength results obtained for all UD laminates when applied locally, within areas of low fibre volume fraction. This verifies the hypothesis that composite compressive strength is largely dominated by weakest-link failure modes, analogous to the failure of ceramics.

The introduction of a deliberate out-of-plane defect did not result in significantly poorer failure

strengths of the UD laminates tested here but did greatly increase the ‘success’ of the experimental test, ‘success’ being defined as a valid failure according to the standard. It is suggested that such defects may be used to control failure locations in large components, greatly reducing inspection time and cost.

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